

EVIDENCE-BASED
TOXICOLOGY

Acceptance note for

TEBT-2025-0008

Submission information table

Submission Title	'Grey literature' in evidence syntheses on Environmental Health & Toxicology (EHT) topics
Submission Reference	TEBT-2025-0008
Handling Editor	Olwenn Martin ORCID 0000-0003-2724-7882 Paul Whaley ORCID 0000-0003-4021-0785
Number of Reviewers	2 editors, 2 peer-reviewers
Submission Type	Method (Protocol for Planned Study)
Preregistration Level	Level 6 (Full Preregistration) (explanation)
Preprint DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14925771
Report Number	3
Evaluation Stage	Acceptance Note
Evaluation Date	7 August 2025
Recommendation	Accept

Editor's Summary of Reviewer Comments

Whilst including the grey literature in systematic review and evidence synthesis is recommended, there is little guidance on how to retrieve and analyse data and documents that have not been published in peer-reviewed journals in many fields, including in environmental health and toxicology. This protocol describes the conduct and analysis of an online survey of those with experience in environmental health and toxicology evidence syntheses with the aim of documenting current practices in this field.

The knowledge aims of the study are clearly described. The editorial triage identified some issues with the description of the methods, including dissemination of the survey, target number of participants and details of the coding strategy data analysis that could all be addressed after peer review. Peer-reviewers commented favourably, making some additional relatively minor suggestions for improving the protocol.

The authors have revised the manuscript in line with the recommendations of the peer reviewers and editors. Crucially, they have offered more details on the process adopted for coding results. As the authors have adopted an inductive approach (emerging themes) for coding, codes cannot be described *a priori*.

The peer review process and authors to reviewers comments highlighted how little attention the challenges related to grey literature in evidence synthesis in environmental health and toxicology have received to date, as it became apparent that the impacts of ignoring said literature are not currently evidenced.

Acceptance Note

This manuscript has been accepted for publication by the handling editor Olwenn Martin after 1 round of revision in response to 1 round of editorial triage and 1 round of peer-review.

For protocols only: In the editor's opinion, this protocol is a [Category 6 preregistration](#) (as this is a survey, no part of the data that will be used to answer the research question yet exists).

According to our Registered Reports policy, the manuscript following from this protocol will be accepted so long as the researchers reasonably adhere to their planned methods.

A complete record of the evaluation reports for this submission can be found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15191530>.